

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Seed scarcity and rapid extinction of deepwater rice (DWR) cultivars in Bangladesh

Z. Islam, Entomology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

DWR used to be the most important crop in the low-lying deltas of Bangladesh. In the late 1960s, more than 500 traditional DWR cultivars were grown on 21% (2.1 million ha) of the nation's rice area. The cultivars had been developed over hundreds of years to suit the specific agroecosystems of diverse DWR areas.

As irrigation facilities in DWR areas expanded with the installation of low-lift pumps and shallow and deep tubewells during the 1970s and 1980s, farmers could grow modern cultivars during the boro season (winter). As a result, the area under DWR in 1990 was reduced to 0.9 million ha, a 56% reduction over 20 yr.

On-station and on-farm research and observations in farmers' fields have

shown that both boro rice and DWR can be grown on the same land with careful planning. A visit in April 1992 to a few DWR areas in the Jamuna floodplain in Mirzapur and Deldwer of Tangail district indicated that farmers did not grow much DWR after modern variety (MV) boro because of the unavailability of DWR seed. Only one of more than 50 farmers selling rice in a remote local market had DWR seed, despite high demand. In the past, DWR seed was abundant at seeding time (Mar/Apr) in the villages and local markets.

We asked groups of farmers to recall the proportion of low-lying areas occupied by different major cropping patterns, and the name of DWR cultivars grown during the 1960s and of those growing at present. In the past, the DWR-based cropping pattern dominated (62%), followed by a jute-based pattern (38%) (Table 1). Expansion of MV boro during the past 20 yr reduced DWR, jute, and nonrice winter crops such as pulses and oilseeds.

The present DWR-based pattern occupies about 8% of the land, the jute pattern 9%, and MV boro pattern 83%. The number of DWR cultivars was also reduced (Table 2). More than 60% of the

cultivars grown in the 1960s have already disappeared. The late-maturing cultivars, which had rapid elongation ability and were suitable for growing in very deep water (>250 cm), have been affected severely.

Scarcity of DWR seed and rapid extinction of cultivars have also been observed in other Bangladesh DWR areas. To increase rice production and to preserve the immense genetic diversity of the traditional DWR cultivars, immediate government intervention is needed for the collection, multiplication, and distribution of DWR seed in the MV boro rice-occupied DWR areas. ■

Table 2. Traditional DWR cultivars grown in the 1960s and in 1991 in selected areas of Mirzapur and Deldwer upazilas of Tangail district, Bangladesh.

Water depth	Cultivar	
	1960s or earlier	1991
Shallow to medium (50-150 cm)	Boron Bawalia	Boron Bawalia
	Senna Bawalia	Senna Bawalia
	Bawalia Digha	Bawalia Digha
	Deshi Digha	Deshi Digha
	Horinga Digha	Senna Digha
	Lokhi Digha	Depho
	Senna Digha	
	Depho	
	Kertikjul	
	Kertik Kaika	
	Rajpal Shonmoti	
Deep (150-250 cm)	Chamara	Chamara
	Dhola Digha	Dhola Digha
	Ejol Digha	Hejol Digha
	Hejol Digha	Haskol Digha
	Haskol Digha	
	Sonna Digha	
Very deep (>250 cm)	Lokhi Kajol	
	Raja Mondol	
	Bugraj	None
	Hamubhanga	
	Haskol Boron	
	Kaitormoni	
	Shuli Boron	
Sheali Boron		

Table 1. Lands occupied by major cropping patterns in the 1960s and in 1991 based on farmer interviews in selected areas of Tangail district, Bangladesh.

Site	Cropping pattern ^a	Cropped area ^b (%)	
		1960s	1991
Shubullar beel (Mirzapur), about 3000 ha	DWR/DWR+aus - rabi/fallow	75	4
	Jute - rabi	25	6
	Boro - fallow/mustard	-	90
Dubail (Deldwer), about 3500 ha	DWR/DWR+aus - rabi/fallow	60	5
	Jute - rabi	40	10
	Boro - fallow/mustard	-	85
Moushakatalia (Deldwer), about 2000 ha	DWR/DWR+aus - rabi/fallow	50	15
	Jute - rabi	50	10
	Boro - fallow/mustard	-	75

^aBoro = winter rice, aus = summer rice, rabi = nonrice winter crops. ^b- = area under boro (local cultivars) was almost nil